

List of All Cited References that were Used

February 6, 2026

References

- [1] AFP. Scammer sentenced for defrauding vulnerable Australians – warrant issued for alleged scheme mastermind | Australian Federal Police, December 2023.
- [2] AFP. Global sting sees Australian offenders arrested for cybercrime and phishing attacks | Australian Federal Police, April 2024.
- [3] Udit Agarwal, Vinay Rishiwal, Sudeep Tanwar, and Mano Yadav. Blockchain and crypto forensics: Investigating crypto frauds. *International Journal of Network Management*, 34(2):e2255, March 2024.
- [4] Cuneyt G. Akcora, Sudhanva Purusotham, Yulia R. Gel, Mitchell Krawiec-Thayer, and Murat Kantarcioglu. How to Not Get Caught When You Launder Money on Blockchain?, 2020.
- [5] Arafat Al-Dhaqm, Richard Adeyemi Ikuesan, Victor R. Kebande, Shukor Abd Razak, George Grispos, Kim-Kwang Raymond Choo, Bander Ali Saleh Al-Rimy, and Abdulrahman A. Alsewari. Digital Forensics Subdomains: The State of the Art and Future Directions. *IEEE access : practical innovations, open solutions*, 9:152476–152502, 2021.
- [6] M. Al Fahdi, N.L. Clarke, and S.M. Furnell. Challenges to digital forensics: A survey of researchers & practitioners attitudes and opinions. In *2013 Information Security for South Africa*, pages 1–8, Johannesburg, South Africa, August 2013. IEEE.
- [7] Bander Ali Saleh Al-rimy, Mohd Aizaini Maarof, and Syed Zainudeen Mohd Shaid. Ransomware threat success factors, taxonomy, and countermeasures: A survey and research directions. *Computers & Security*, 74:144–166, May 2018.

- [8] Noorulain Ashraf, Danish Mahmood, Muath A. Obaidat, Ghufuran Ahmed, and Adnan Akhunzada. Criminal Behavior Identification Using Social Media Forensics. *Electronics*, 11(19):3162, October 2022.
- [9] Hany F. Atlam, Ndifon Ekuri, Muhammad Ajmal Azad, and Harjinder Singh Lallie. Blockchain Forensics: A Systematic Literature Review of Techniques, Applications, Challenges, and Future Directions. *Electronics*, 13(17):3568, September 2024.
- [10] Heewon Baek, Minwook Lee, and Hyoungshick Kim. CryptoLLM: Harnessing the Power of LLMs to Detect Cryptographic API Misuse. In Joaquin Garcia-Alfaro, Rafał Kozik, Michał Choraś, and Sokratis Katsikas, editors, *Computer Security – ESORICS 2024*, volume 14982, pages 353–373. Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham, 2024.
- [11] Raffaella Barone and Donato Masciandaro. Cryptocurrency or usury? Crime and alternative money laundering techniques. *European Journal of Law and Economics*, 47(2):233–254, April 2019.
- [12] Fillipe Barros Rodrigues, William Ferreira Giozza, Robson De Oliveira Albuquerque, and Luis Javier García Villalba. Natural Language Processing Applied to Forensics Information Extraction With Transformers and Graph Visualization. *IEEE Transactions on Computational Social Systems*, 11(4):4727–4743, 2022.
- [13] Massimo Bartoletti, Salvatore Carta, Tiziana Cimoli, and Roberto Saia. Dissecting Ponzi schemes on Ethereum: Identification, analysis, and impact, August 2019.
- [14] Massimo Bartoletti, Stefano Lande, Livio Pompianu, and Andrea Bracciali. A general framework for blockchain analytics. In *Proceedings of the 1st Workshop on Scalable and Resilient Infrastructures for Distributed Ledgers*, pages 1–6, Las Vegas Nevada, December 2017. ACM.
- [15] Massimo Bartoletti, Barbara Pes, and Sergio Serusi. Data Mining for Detecting Bitcoin Ponzi Schemes. In *2018 Crypto Valley Conference on Blockchain Technology (CVCBT)*, pages 75–84, Zug, June 2018. IEEE.
- [16] BBC. Police bust global cyber gang accused of industrial-scale fraud. April 2024.
- [17] Beatrice Oyinkansola Adelokun, Ebere Ruth Onwubuariri, Gbenga Adeniyi Adeniran, and Afari Ntiakoh. Enhancing fraud detection in

- accounting through AI: Techniques and case studies. *Finance & Accounting Research Journal*, 6(6):978–999, June 2024.
- [18] Nicole Lang Beebe and Jan Guynes Clark. A hierarchical, objectives-based framework for the digital investigations process. *Digital Investigation*, 2(2):147–167, June 2005.
- [19] Nils Begou, Jérémy Vinoy, Andrzej Duda, and Maciej Korczyński. Exploring the Dark Side of AI: Advanced Phishing Attack Design and Deployment Using ChatGPT. In *2023 IEEE Conference on Communications and Network Security (CNS)*, pages 1–6, Orlando, FL, USA, October 2023. IEEE.
- [20] Prabhu R. Bevinamarad and M.S. Shirdonkar. Audio Forgery Detection Techniques: Present and Past Review. In *2020 4th International Conference on Trends in Electronics and Informatics (ICOEI)(48184)*, pages 613–618, Tirunelveli, India, June 2020. IEEE.
- [21] Alex Biryukov, Dmitry Khovratovich, and Ivan Pustogarov. Deanonymisation of clients in Bitcoin P2P network, July 2014.
- [22] Alex Biryukov and Sergei Tikhomirov. Deanonymization and Linkability of Cryptocurrency Transactions Based on Network Analysis. In *2019 IEEE European Symposium on Security and Privacy (EuroS&P)*, pages 172–184, Stockholm, Sweden, June 2019. IEEE.
- [23] Jildau Borwell, Jurjen Jansen, and Wouter Stol. Comparing the victimization impact of cybercrime and traditional crime: Literature review and future research directions. *Journal of Digital Social Research*, 3(3):85–110, October 2021.
- [24] Sami Bourouis, Roobaea Alroobaea, Abdullah M. Alharbi, Murad Andejany, and Saeed Rubaiee. Recent Advances in Digital Multimedia Tampering Detection for Forensics Analysis. *Symmetry*, 12(11):1811, November 2020.
- [25] Frank Breiting, Jan-Niclas Hilgert, Christopher Hargreaves, John Sheppard, Rebekah Overdorf, and Mark Scanlon. DFRWS EU 10-year review and future directions in Digital Forensic Research. *Forensic Science International: Digital Investigation*, 48:301685, March 2024.
- [26] Brian Krebs. Tagging and Tracking Espionage Botnets. Technical report, KrebsSecurity, June 2012.

- [27] Brian Krebs. U.K. Arrest in ‘SMS Bandits’ Phishing Service – Krebs on Security, January 2021.
- [28] Brian Krebs. Warning the World of a Ticking Time Bomb – Krebs on Security, March 2021.
- [29] Brian Krebs. 3CX Breach Was a Double Supply Chain Compromise – Krebs on Security, April 2023.
- [30] Brian Krebs. Arrests in \$400M SIM-Swap Tied to Heist at FTX? – Krebs on Security, February 2024.
- [31] Brian Krebs. Canadian Man Stuck in Triangle of E-Commerce Fraud – Krebs on Security, January 2024.
- [32] Brian Krebs. Fla. Man Charged in SIM-Swapping Spree is Key Suspect in Hacker Groups Oktapus, Scattered Spider – Krebs on Security, January 2024.
- [33] Brian Krebs. Owners of 1-Time Passcode Theft Service Plead Guilty – Krebs on Security, September 2024.
- [34] Brian Krebs. U.S. Indicts 2 Top Russian Hackers, Sanctions Cryptex – Krebs on Security, September 2024.
- [35] Brian Krebs. Alleged Extortioner of Psychotherapy Patients Faces Trial – Krebs on Security, November 2023.
- [36] Josh Brunty. Validation of forensic tools and methods: A primer for the digital forensics examiner. *WIREs Forensic Science*, 5(2):e1474, 2023.
- [37] Brian Carrier and Eugene Spafford. An Event-Based Digital Forensic Investigation Framework. *Digital Forensic Research Workshop (DFRWS)*, 4(1):1–15, January 2004.
- [38] Eoghan Casey. *Digital Evidence and Computer Crime: Forensic Science, Computers, and the Internet*. Academic Press, Inc., USA, 3rd edition, April 2011.
- [39] Fran Casino, Thomas K. Dasaklis, Georgios P. Spathoulas, Marios Anagnostopoulos, Amrita Ghosal, Istvan Borocz, Agusti Solanas, Mauro Conti, and Constantinos Patsakis. Research Trends, Challenges, and Emerging Topics in Digital Forensics: A Review of Reviews. *IEEE access : practical innovations, open solutions*, 10:25464–25493, 2022.

- [40] Catalin Cimpanu. Belgian and Dutch police take down encrypted criminal chat platform Sky ECC, September 2021.
- [41] National Anti-Scam Centre. Australians better protected as reported scam losses fell by almost 26 per cent. <https://www.nasc.gov.au/news/australians-better-protected-as-reported-scam-losses-fell-by-almost-26-per-cent>, March 2025.
- [42] Chainalysis. 2024 Crypto Crime webinar series, 2024.
- [43] Chainalysis. Phishing-as-a-Service Provider LabHost Disrupted, April 2024.
- [44] Chainalysis. The-2024-crypto-crime-report-release, 2024.
- [45] Chainalysis. The 2025 Crypto Crime Report. Technical report, 2025.
- [46] Vasilka Chergarova, Vinicius Arcanjo, Mel Tomeo, Jeronimo Bezerra, Luis Marin Vera, and Anthony Uloa. Cryptocurrency fraud: A study on the characteristics of criminals who are using fake profiles on a social media platform to persuade individuals to invest into cryptocurrency. *Issues In Information Systems*, 23(3):252–252, 2022.
- [47] Sneha Chinivar, Roopa M.S., Arunalatha J.S., and Venugopal K.R. Online offensive behaviour in socialmedia: Detection approaches, comprehensive review and future directions. *Entertainment Computing*, 45:100544, March 2023.
- [48] Jenny Cifuentes, Ana Lucila Sandoval Orozco, and Luis Javier García Villalba. A survey of artificial intelligence strategies for automatic detection of sexually explicit videos. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 81(3):3205–3222, January 2022.
- [49] Smaranda Cioban, Adela Răzvana Lazăr, Claudia Bacter, and Adrian Hatos. Adolescent Deviance and Cyber-Deviance. A Systematic Literature Review. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12:748006, October 2021.
- [50] Australian Competition and Consumer Commission. Scam losses decline, but more work to do as Australians lose \$2.7 billion. <https://www.accc.gov.au/media-release/scam-losses-decline-but-more-work-to-do-as-australians-lose-27-billion>, April 2024.
- [51] Mauro Conti, Ankit Gangwal, and Sushmita Ruj. On the economic significance of ransomware campaigns: A Bitcoin transactions perspective. *Computers & Security*, 79:162–189, November 2018.

- [52] Jack Cook and Jared Scott Cook. The dual faces of social media: Connectivity and fraud in the digital age. *SAM Advanced Management Journal*, December 2024.
- [53] Kelton A.P. Da Costa, João P. Papa, Leandro A. Passos, Danilo Colombo, Javier Del Ser, Khan Muhammad, and Victor Hugo C. De Albuquerque. A critical literature survey and prospects on tampering and anomaly detection in image data. *Applied Soft Computing*, 97:106727, December 2020.
- [54] David Adler. *Silk Road: The Dark Side of Cryptocurrency*, February 2018.
- [55] Kevin Delmolino, Mitchell Arnett, Ahmed Kosba, Andrew Miller, and Elaine Shi. Step by Step Towards Creating a Safe Smart Contract: Lessons and Insights from a Cryptocurrency Lab. In Jeremy Clark, Sarah Meiklejohn, Peter Y.A. Ryan, Dan Wallach, Michael Brenner, and Kurt Rohloff, editors, *Financial Cryptography and Data Security*, volume 9604, pages 79–94. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2016.
- [56] Dina Temple-Raston and Will Jarvis. The ‘game-changing’ attitude behind a very creative dark web takedown, September 2023.
- [57] Daniel Dolejška, Michal Koutenský, Vladimír Veselý, and Jan Pluskal. Busting up Monopoly: Methods for modern darknet marketplace forensics. *Forensic Science International: Digital Investigation*, 46:301604, October 2023.
- [58] Himanshu Dubey, Shobha Bhatt, and Lokesh Negi. Digital Forensics Techniques and Trends: A Review. *The International Arab Journal of Information Technology*, 20(4):644–654, 2023.
- [59] Sahil Dudani, Ibrahim Baggili, David Raymond, and Randolph Marchany. The current state of cryptocurrency forensics. *Forensic Science International: Digital Investigation*, 46:301576, September 2023.
- [60] Daniel Dupuis, Deborah Smith, and Kimberly Gleason. Old frauds with a new sauce: Digital assets and space transition. *Journal of Financial Crime*, 30(1):205–220, January 2023.
- [61] ENFSI. Best Practice Manual for the Forensic Examination of Digital Technology With the financial support of the Prevention of and Fight

- against Crime Programme European Commission-Directorate-General Home Affairs, 2015.
- [62] Eurojust. Dismantling EncroChat - Press Conference 02/07/20 EN | Eurojust, July 2020.
- [63] Europol. International investigation disrupts phishing-as-a-service platform LabHost – LabHost facilitated the phishing of users of hundreds of financial institutions worldwide for monthly subscription fee.
- [64] Hussam N. Fakhouri, Mohammad A. AlSharaiah, Ahmad K. Al Hwaitat, Mohammad Alkalaileh, and Fawzi Fayez Dweikat. Overview of Challenges Faced by Digital Forensic. In *2024 2nd International Conference on Cyber Resilience (ICCR)*, pages 1–8, Dubai, United Arab Emirates, February 2024. IEEE.
- [65] Polra Victor Falade. Decoding the Threat Landscape : ChatGPT, FraudGPT, and WormGPT in Social Engineering Attacks. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Computer Science, Engineering and Information Technology*, 9(5):185–198, October 2023.
- [66] FinCEN. Proposal of Special Measure Regarding Convertible Virtual Currency Mixing, as a Class of Transactions of Primary Money Laundering Concern, October 2023.
- [67] Catarina Fonseca, Samuel Moreira, and Inês Guedes. Online Consumer Fraud Victimization and Reporting: A Quantitative Study of the Predictors and Motives. *Victims & Offenders*, 17(5):756–780, July 2022.
- [68] Fortra. Phishing-as-a-Service Profile: LabHost Threat Actor Group, February 2024.
- [69] Simson L. Garfinkel. Digital forensics research: The next 10 years. *Digital Investigation*, 7:S64–S73, August 2010.
- [70] Gary Palmer. A Road Map for Digital Forensic Research: Report from the First Digital Forensic Workshop, 2001.
- [71] Rafael González Arias, Javier Bermejo Higuera, J. Javier Rainer Granados, Juan Ramón Bermejo Higuera, and Juan Antonio Sicilia Montalvo. Systematic Review: Anti-Forensic Computer Techniques. *Applied Sciences*, 14(12):5302, June 2024.

- [72] Cinthya Grajeda, Frank Breitinger, and Ibrahim Baggili. Availability of datasets for digital forensics And what is missing. *Digital Investigation*, 22(S):S94–S105, August 2017.
- [73] Ankita Guleria, Kewal Krishan, Vishal Sharma, and Tanuj Kanchan. ChatGPT: Forensic, legal, and ethical issues. *Medicine, Science and the Law*, 64(2):150–156, April 2024.
- [74] Vikram S. Harichandran, Frank Breitinger, Ibrahim Baggili, and Andrew Marrington. A cyber forensics needs analysis survey: Revisiting the domain’s needs a decade later. *Computers & Security*, 57:1–13, March 2016.
- [75] Heemeng Ho, Ryan Ko, and Lorraine Mazerolle. Situational Crime Prevention (SCP) techniques to prevent and control cybercrimes: A focused systematic review. *Computers & Security*, 115:102611, April 2022.
- [76] N. Hoque, Monowar H. Bhuyan, R.C. Baishya, D.K. Bhattacharyya, and J.K. Kalita. Network attacks: Taxonomy, tools and systems. *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, 40:307–324, April 2014.
- [77] Lars Hornuf, Theresa Kück, and Armin Schwienbacher. Initial coin offerings, information disclosure, and fraud. *Small Business Economics*, 58(4):1741–1759, April 2022.
- [78] INTERPOL. Guidelines For Digital Forensics First Responders, 2021.
- [79] Angela S.M. Irwin and Adam B. Turner. Illicit Bitcoin transactions: Challenges in getting to the who, what, when and where. *Journal of Money Laundering Control*, 21(3):297–313, July 2018.
- [80] ISO. ISO/IEC 27041:2015(en), Information technology — Security techniques — Guidance on assuring suitability and adequacy of incident investigative method, 2015.
- [81] Janet Williams. ACPO Good Practice Guide for Digital Evidence (Version 5), 2012.
- [82] Abdul Rehman Javed, Waqas Ahmed, Mamoun Alazab, Zunera Jalil, Kashif Kifayat, and Thippa Reddy Gadekallu. A Comprehensive Survey on Computer Forensics: State-of-the-Art, Tools, Techniques, Challenges, and Future Directions. *IEEE access : practical innovations, open solutions*, 10:11065–11089, 2022.

- [83] Josh Kamps and Bennett Kleinberg. To the moon: Defining and detecting cryptocurrency pump-and-dumps. *Crime Science*, 7(1):18, December 2018.
- [84] Kara Nance, Brian Hay, and Matt Bishop. Digital Forensics: Defining a Research Agenda. In *2009 42nd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, pages 1–6, Waikoloa, Hawaii, USA, 2009. IEEE.
- [85] Harpreet Kaur and Neeru Jindal. Image and Video Forensics: A Critical Survey. *Wireless Personal Communications*, 112(2):1281–1302, May 2020.
- [86] K Kent, S Chevalier, T Grance, and H Dang. Guide to integrating forensic techniques into incident response. Technical Report NIST SP 800-86, National Institute of Standards and Technology, Gaithersburg, MD, 2006.
- [87] David S. Kerr, Karen A. Loveland, Katherine Taken Smith, and Lawrence Murphy Smith. Cryptocurrency Risks, Fraud Cases, and Financial Performance. *Risks*, 11(3):51, March 2023.
- [88] Sesha Kethineni and Ying Cao. The Rise in Popularity of Cryptocurrency and Associated Criminal Activity. *International Criminal Justice Review*, 30(3):325–344, September 2020.
- [89] Suleman Khan, Abdullah Gani, Ainuddin Wahid Abdul Wahab, Muhammad Shiraz, and Iftikhar Ahmad. Network forensics: Review, taxonomy, and open challenges. *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, 66:214–235, May 2016.
- [90] Romi Kher, Siri Terjesen, and Chen Liu. Blockchain, Bitcoin, and ICOs: A review and research agenda. *Small Business Economics*, 56(4):1699–1720, April 2021.
- [91] Minsoo Kim, Doyoun Kim, Yunji Park, and Doowon Jeong. Development of an Expert Chatbot for Digital Forensics Using RAG Model Implementation. In *2024 International Conference on Platform Technology and Service (PlatCon)*, pages 182–187, Jeju, Korea, Republic of, August 2024. IEEE.
- [92] Ahmed Kosba, Andrew Miller, Elaine Shi, Zikai Wen, and Charalampos Papamanthou. Hawk: The Blockchain Model of Cryptography and

- Privacy-Preserving Smart Contracts. In *2016 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*, pages 839–858, San Jose, CA, May 2016. IEEE.
- [93] Chin Kuo and Seng-Su Tsang. Constructing an Investment Scam Detection Model Based on Emotional Fluctuations Throughout the Investment Scam Life Cycle. *Deviant Behavior*, 45(2):204–225, February 2024.
- [94] David Lacey, Andrew Campbell, Sigi Goode, and Brad Ridout. *The Cyberpsychology of Deception: A Mini Review of the Psychological Factors Influencing Scam Compliance*. EasyChair, 2024.
- [95] David Lacey, Sigi Goode, Jerry Pawada, and Dennis Gibson. The application of scam compliance models to investment fraud offending. *Journal of Criminological Research, Policy and Practice*, 6(1):65–81, April 2020.
- [96] Shancang Li and Yifan Liu. Human-centric Artificial Intelligence enabled Digital Images and Videos Forensic Triage. In *2023 International Conference on Human-Centered Cognitive Systems (HCCS)*, pages 1–5, December 2023.
- [97] Kevin Liao, Ziming Zhao, Adam Doupe, and Gail-Joon Ahn. Behind closed doors: Measurement and analysis of CryptoLocker ransoms in Bitcoin. In *2016 APWG Symposium on Electronic Crime Research (eCrime)*, pages 1–13, Toronto, ON, Canada, June 2016. IEEE.
- [98] Chang-Yi Lin, Hsiang-Kai Liao, and Fu-Ching Tsai. A Systematic Review of Detecting Illicit Bitcoin Transactions. *Procedia Computer Science*, 207:3217–3225, 2022.
- [99] Leandro Loffi, Gerson Luiz Camillo, Cristiano Antonio De Souza, Carla Merkle Westphall, and Carlos Becker Westphall. Management of the Chain of Custody of Digital Evidence Using Blockchain and Self-Sovereign Identities: A Systematic Literature Review. *IEEE access : practical innovations, open solutions*, 13:77804–77832, 2025.
- [100] Loi Luu, Duc-Hiep Chu, Hrishi Olickel, Prateek Saxena, and Aquinas Hobor. Making Smart Contracts Smarter. In *Proceedings of the 2016 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security*, pages 254–269, Vienna Austria, October 2016. ACM.

- [101] Mark Reith, Clint Carr, and Gregg Gunsch. An Examination of Digital Forensic Models, 2002.
- [102] Melissa Martineau, Elena Spiridon, and Mary Aiken. A Comprehensive Framework for Cyber Behavioral Analysis Based on a Systematic Review of Cyber Profiling Literature. *Forensic Sciences*, 3(3):452–477, July 2023.
- [103] Mohd Zaki Mas’ud, Aslinda Hassan, Wahidah Md. Shah, Shekh Faisal Abdul-Latip, Rabiah Ahmad, Aswami Ariffin, and Zahri Yunos. A Review of Digital Forensics Framework for Blockchain in Cryptocurrency Technology. In *2021 3rd International Cyber Resilience Conference (CRC)*, pages 1–6, Langkawi Island, Malaysia, January 2021. IEEE.
- [104] Sarah Meiklejohn, Marjori Pomarole, Grant Jordan, Kirill Levchenko, Damon McCoy, Geoffrey M. Voelker, and Stefan Savage. A fistful of Bitcoins: Characterizing payments among men with no names. *Communications of the ACM*, 59(4):86–93, March 2016.
- [105] Norulzahrah Mohd Zainudin, Nor Asiakin Hasbullah, Muslihah Wook, Suzaimah Ramli, and Noor Afiza Mat Razali. DIGITAL FORENSIC READINESS IN CYBERSECURITY: A REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE AND IDENTIFICATION OF KNOWLEDGE GAPS. *Zulfaqar Journal of Defence Science, Engineering & Technology*, 7(1):1–8, June 2024.
- [106] Anthony Morgan and Alexandra Voce. The cost of espionage. August 2025.
- [107] Muaadh Mukred, Umi Asma’ Mokhtar, Fahad Abdullah Moafa, Abdu Gumaei, Ali Safaa Sadiq, and Abdulaleem Al-Othmani. The roots of digital aggression: Exploring cyber-violence through a systematic literature review. *International Journal of Information Management Data Insights*, 4(2):100281, November 2024.
- [108] Ibrahim Nadir and Taimur Bakhshi. Contemporary cybercrime: A taxonomy of ransomware threats & mitigation techniques. In *2018 International Conference on Computing, Mathematics and Engineering Technologies (iCoMET)*, pages 1–7. IEEE, March 2018.
- [109] Souradip Nath, Keb Summers, Jaejong Baek, and Gail-Joon Ahn. Digital Evidence Chain of Custody: Navigating New Realities of Digital

- Forensics. In *2024 IEEE 6th International Conference on Trust, Privacy and Security in Intelligent Systems, and Applications (TPS-ISA)*, pages 11–20, October 2024.
- [110] New Zealand Police. Op Orca — smishing scam smashed | New Zealand Police, March 2024.
- [111] Ericmoore Ngharamike, Li-Minn Ang, Kah Phooi Seng, and Mingzhong Wang. ENF Based Digital Multimedia Forensics: Survey, Application, Challenges and Future Work. *IEEE access : practical innovations, open solutions*, 11:101241–101272, 2023.
- [112] Tien N. Nguyen and Raymond Choo. Human-in-the-Loop XAI-enabled Vulnerability Detection, Investigation, and Mitigation. In *2021 36th IEEE/ACM International Conference on Automated Software Engineering (ASE)*, pages 1210–1212, November 2021.
- [113] Bruce Nikkel. Fintech forensics: Criminal investigation and digital evidence in financial technologies. *Forensic Science International: Digital Investigation*, 33:200908, June 2020.
- [114] Antonia Nisioti, Alexios Mylonas, Paul D. Yoo, and Vasilios Katos. From Intrusion Detection to Attacker Attribution: A Comprehensive Survey of Unsupervised Methods. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 20(4):3369–3388, 2018.
- [115] Gareth Norris, Alexandra Brookes, and David Dowell. The Psychology of Internet Fraud Victimization: A Systematic Review. *Journal of Police and Criminal Psychology*, 34(3):231–245, September 2019.
- [116] Daniel E. O’Leary. Open Information Enterprise Transactions: Business Intelligence and Wash and Spoof Transactions in Blockchain and Social Commerce. *Intelligent Systems in Accounting, Finance and Management*, 25(3):148–158, July 2018.
- [117] Filippo Perrina, Francesco Marchiori, Mauro Conti, and Nino Vincenzo Verde. AGIR: Automating Cyber Threat Intelligence Reporting with Natural Language Generation. In *2023 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (BigData)*, pages 3053–3062, Sorrento, Italy, December 2023. IEEE.
- [118] Emmanuel S. Pilli, R.C. Joshi, and Rajdeep Niyogi. Network forensic frameworks: Survey and research challenges. *Digital Investigation*, 7(1-2):14–27, October 2010.

- [119] Darren Quick and Kim-Kwang Raymond Choo. Impacts of increasing volume of digital forensic data: A survey and future research challenges. *Digital Investigation*, 11(4):273–294, December 2014.
- [120] Sampath Rajapaksha, Ruby Rani, and Erisa Karafili. A RAG-Based Question-Answering Solution for Cyber-Attack Investigation and Attribution, 2024.
- [121] Judith A. Redi, Wiem Taktak, and Jean-Luc Dugelay. Digital image forensics: A booklet for beginners. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 51(1):133–162, January 2011.
- [122] Nathan Reiff, Summer Anderson, and Pete Rathburn. Bitcoin’s Share of Global Wealth: An Analysis, December 2025.
- [123] Perri Reynolds and Angela S.M. Irwin. Tracking digital footprints: Anonymity within the bitcoin system:. *Journal of Money Laundering Control*, 20(2):172–189, May 2017.
- [124] Sam Rogers. International Scammers Steal Over \$1 Trillion in 12 Months in New Global State of Scams Report, November 2024.
- [125] Dorit Ron and Adi Shamir. Quantitative Analysis of the Full Bitcoin Transaction Graph. In David Hutchison, Takeo Kanade, Josef Kittler, Jon M. Kleinberg, Friedemann Mattern, John C. Mitchell, Moni Naor, Oscar Nierstrasz, C. Pandu Rangan, Bernhard Steffen, Madhu Sudan, Demetri Terzopoulos, Doug Tygar, Moshe Y. Vardi, Gerhard Weikum, and Ahmad-Reza Sadeghi, editors, *Financial Cryptography and Data Security*, volume 7859, pages 6–24. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2013.
- [126] Sayak Saha Roy, Krishna Vamsi Naragam, and Shirin Nilizadeh. Generating Phishing Attacks using ChatGPT, May 2023.
- [127] Akram Hatem Saber, Mohd Ayyub Khan, and Basim Galeb Mejbil. A Survey on Image Forgery Detection Using Different Forensic Approaches. *Advances in Science, Technology and Engineering Systems Journal*, 5(3):361–370, 2020.
- [128] Sabuj Saha, Ahmed Rizvan Hasan, Alvi Mahmud, Nujhat Ahmed, Nahida Parvin, and Hemal Karmakar. Cryptocurrency and financial crimes: A bibliometric analysis and future research agenda. *Multidisciplinary Reviews*, 7(8):2024168, May 2024.

- [129] Shreya Sangal, Gaurav Duggal, and Achint Nigam. Blockchain’s double-edged sword: Thematic review of illegal activities using blockchain. *Journal of Information, Communication and Ethics in Society*, 22(1):58–81, March 2024.
- [130] Mark Scanlon, Frank Breitingger, Christopher Hargreaves, Jan-Niclas Hilgert, and John Sheppard. ChatGPT for digital forensic investigation: The good, the bad, and the unknown. *Forensic Science International: Digital Investigation*, 46:301609, October 2023.
- [131] Mircea Constantin Șcheau, Simona Liliana Crăciunescu, Iulia Brici, and Monica Violeta Achim. A Cryptocurrency Spectrum Short Analysis. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 13(8):184, August 2020.
- [132] Séamus Ó Ciardhuáin. An Extended Model of Cybercrime Investigations., 2004.
- [133] Searchlight Cyber. The LockBit Takedown, May 2024.
- [134] Zeinab Shahbazi and Yung-Cheol Byun. NLP-Based Digital Forensic Analysis for Online Social Network Based on System Security. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(12):7027, June 2022.
- [135] Yuxi Shang, Zhongxian Wu, Xiaoyu Du, Yanbin Jiang, Beibei Ma, and Meihong Chi. The psychology of the internet fraud victimization of older adults: A systematic review. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13:912242, September 2022.
- [136] Nitin Arvind Shelke and Singara Singh Kasana. A comprehensive survey on passive techniques for digital video forgery detection. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 80(4):6247–6310, February 2021.
- [137] Robinson Tombari Sibe and Christian Kaunert. Digital Evidence, Digital Forensics, and Digital Forensic Readiness. In Robinson Tombari Sibe and Christian Kaunert, editors, *Cybercrime, Digital Forensic Readiness, and Financial Crime Investigation in Nigeria*, pages 57–83. Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham, 2024.
- [138] Leslie F. Sikos. Packet analysis for network forensics: A comprehensive survey. *Forensic Science International: Digital Investigation*, 32:200892, March 2020.

- [139] K. Sitara and B.M. Mehtre. Digital video tampering detection: An overview of passive techniques. *Digital Investigation*, 18:8–22, September 2016.
- [140] Michele Spagnuolo, Federico Maggi, and Stefano Zanero. BitIodine: Extracting Intelligence from the Bitcoin Network. In Nicolas Christin and Reihaneh Safavi-Naini, editors, *Financial Cryptography and Data Security*, volume 8437, pages 457–468. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2014.
- [141] Loretta J. Stalans and Christopher M. Donner. Explaining Why Cybercrime Occurs: Criminological and Psychological Theories. In Hamid Jahankhani, editor, *Cyber Criminology*, pages 25–45. Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2018.
- [142] Kevin F. Steinmetz. The Identification of a Model Victim for Social Engineering: A Qualitative Analysis. *Victims & Offenders*, 16(4):540–564, May 2021.
- [143] Dongming Sun, Xiaolu Zhang, Kim-Kwang Raymond Choo, Liang Hu, and Feng Wang. NLP-based digital forensic investigation platform for online communications. *Computers & Security*, 104:102210, May 2021.
- [144] Fabian Maximilian Johannes Teichmann and Marie-Christin Falker. Cryptocurrencies and financial crime: Solutions from Liechtenstein. *Journal of Money Laundering Control*, 24(4):775–788, June 2020.
- [145] Ali Teymourian, Andrew M. Webb, Taha Gharaibeh, Arushi Ghildiyal, and Ibrahim Baggili. SoK: Come Together – Unifying Security, Information Theory, and Cognition for a Mixed Reality Deception Attack Ontology & Analysis Framework. pages 1475–1492, 2025.
- [146] Piret Tonurist and Angela Hanson. Anticipatory innovation governance: Shaping the future through proactive policy making. OECD Working Papers on Public Governance 44, December 2020.
- [147] Trend Micro Research. The Fall of LabHost: Law Enforcement Shuts Down Phishing Service Provider, April 2024.
- [148] Arianna Trozze, Josh Kamps, Eray Arda Akartuna, Florian J. Hetzel, Bennett Kleinberg, Toby Davies, and Shane D. Johnson. Cryptocurrencies and future financial crime. *Crime Science*, 11(1):1, December 2022.

- [149] Adam B. Turner, Stephen McCombie, and Allon J. Uhlmann. A target-centric intelligence approach to WannaCry 2.0. *Journal of Money Laundering Control*, 22(4):646–665, October 2019.
- [150] David Okore Ukwem and Murat Karabatak. Review of NLP-based Systems in Digital Forensics and Cybersecurity. In *2021 9th International Symposium on Digital Forensics and Security (ISDFS)*, pages 1–9, Elazig, Turkey, June 2021. IEEE.
- [151] Ubaid Ullah, Sonia Laudanna, P. Vinod, Andrea Di Sorbo, Corrado Aaron Visaggio, and Gerardo Canfora. Beyond Words: Stylo-metric Analysis for Detecting AI Manipulation on Social Media. In Joaquin Garcia-Alfaro, Rafał Kozik, Michał Choraś, and Sokratis Katsikas, editors, *Computer Security – ESORICS 2024*, volume 14982, pages 208–228. Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham, 2024.
- [152] United States Court of Appeal. UNITED STATES OF AMERICA v. ROSS WILLIAM ULBRICHT DREAD PIRATE ROBERTS SILK ROAD SEALED DEFENDANT DPR (2017), May 2017.
- [153] US Department of the Treasury. Treasury Takes Coordinated Actions Against Illicit Russian Virtual Currency Exchanges and Cybercrime Facilitator, September 2024.
- [154] US District Court of South Carolina. Phantom Secure Indictment, January 2017.
- [155] US District Court Southern District of California. Operation Trojan Shield Indictment, September 2019.
- [156] US DOT. Treasury Sanctions Mixer Used by the DPRK to Launder Stolen Virtual Currency, December 2024.
- [157] US DOT. U.S. Treasury Issues First-Ever Sanctions on a Virtual Currency Mixer, Targets DPRK Cyber Threats, December 2024.
- [158] US DOT. U.S. Treasury Sanctions Notorious Virtual Currency Mixer Tornado Cash, December 2024.
- [159] US Office of Foreign Assets Control. Countering America’s Adversaries Through Sanctions Act-Related Sanctions | Office of Foreign Assets Control, December 2024.

- [160] US Office of Public Affairs. Office of Public Affairs | Three Germans Who Allegedly Operated Dark Web Marketplace with Over 1 Million Users Face U.S. Narcotics and Money Laundering Charges | United States Department of Justice, May 2019.
- [161] Rolf van Wegberg, Jan-Jaap Oerlemans, and Oskar van Deventer. Bitcoin money laundering: Mixed results? An explorative study on money laundering of cybercrime proceeds using bitcoin. *Journal of Financial Crime*, 25(2):419–435, May 2018.
- [162] Marie Vasek and Tyler Moore. There’s No Free Lunch, Even Using Bitcoin: Tracking the Popularity and Profits of Virtual Currency Scams. In Rainer Böhme and Tatsuaki Okamoto, editors, *Financial Cryptography and Data Security*, volume 8975, pages 44–61. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2015.
- [163] Worldometer. GDP by Country (2024), January 2026.
- [164] Lei Wu, Yufeng Hu, Yajin Zhou, Haoyu Wang, Xiapu Luo, Zhi Wang, Fan Zhang, and Kui Ren. Towards Understanding and Demystifying Bitcoin Mixing Services. In *Proceedings of the Web Conference 2021*, pages 33–44, Ljubljana Slovenia, April 2021. ACM.
- [165] Madelyne Xiao and Jonathan Mayer. SoK: Machine Learning for Misinformation Detection. pages 5247–5266, 2025.
- [166] Yagmur Yigit, William J Buchanan, Madjid G Tehrani, and Leandros Maglaras. Review of Generative AI Methods in Cybersecurity, 2024.
- [167] Zhipeng Yin, Zichong Wang, Weifeng Xu, Jun Zhuang, Pallab Mozumder, Antoinette Smith, and Wenbin Zhang. Digital Forensics in the Age of Large Language Models, 2025.
- [168] Haaron Yousaf, George Kappos, and Sarah Meiklejohn. Tracing transactions across cryptocurrency ledgers. In *Proceedings of the 28th USENIX Conference on Security Symposium, SEC’19*, pages 837–850, USA, August 2019. USENIX Association.
- [169] Md Zakir Hossain Zamil and Tahir M. Khan. AI-Driven Digital Evidence Triage in Digital Forensics: A Comprehensive Review. In *2025 13th International Symposium on Digital Forensics and Security (ISDFS)*, pages 1–6, April 2025.